

PERINATAL OUTCOMES ASSOCIATED WITH SUBCHORIONIC HEMATOMA AND LOW-DOSE ASPIRIN IN WOMEN OF EARLY GESTATION

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Abstract. *Retrochorial hematoma is a pathology of the first trimester of pregnancy, leading to complications of perinatal outcomes. Low doses of aspirin improve blood flow in early gestation, helping to reduce perinatal outcomes.*

Keywords: *subchorionic hematoma, low-dose aspirin, pregnant women, perinatal outcomes.*

SCH in first-trimester pregnancies has been estimated to range from 0.46% to 22% in the general obstetric community over the last decade [1-3]. Subchorionic hemorrhage (SCH) is a fluid collection in the uterine cavity produced by trophoblast separation from the uterine wall [2]. These areas also include small echogenic objects, which are assumed to be blood clots. Ultrasonography is most commonly used to diagnose SCH. Mantoni and Pedersen first characterized the patterns of SCH in 1981. Since then, ultrasonographic equipment has greatly advanced, resulting in more reliable findings and diagnosis [4].

Blood that has accumulated between the chorionic membrane and the uterine wall as a result of the chorion's separation from the endometrium is known as a subchorionic hematoma (SCH) [5,6]. It is both the most typical first-trimester bleeding cause and the most typical sonographic abnormalities in pregnant women with symptoms of imminent miscarriage [1,7]. In the general obstetric population, the incidence of SCH is thought to vary from 1.7% to 3.1%, but in pregnant women who exhibit signs of an impending abortion, it may reach 20% [1,8].

The clinical importance of finding a SCH in early pregnancy has long been debated. Early pregnancies with identified SCH are associated with adverse outcomes such as spontaneous abortions, fetal death, and premature birth. In patients with threatening abortions, a SCH is associated with an increased chance of miscarriage [8]. SCH have also been linked to premature birth via unknown physiological pathways, and the presence of a SCH in early pregnancy coincides with a twofold increase in pregnancy loss [9,10].

The exact effect of SCH on pregnancy outcomes is still unknown, as there is ongoing debate regarding the risk of abortion in early pregnancies complicated by SCH as well as the clinical significance of the size of SCH in terms of adverse pregnancy outcomes. SCH is a common abnormality that has been suggested to be associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes such as early pregnancy loss, placental abruption, and preterm delivery [7,10-16].

This is noteworthy in light of the fact that among the several techniques for measuring the size of SCH described in the literature, this one was deemed to have the strongest correlation with the outcome of the first trimester of pregnancy [17].

Some results are consistent with the previously reported links between the presence and/or size of SCH and unfavorable pregnancy outcomes, such as a higher risk of miscarriage [1,7,8,14,18,19], IUGR [18], first trimester vaginal bleeding [6, 20], placental abruption [1,6,7], preterm delivery [1,6,7], and fetal growth restriction [1,7]. In a meta-analysis of seven studies involving 1,735 women with SCH and 70,703 controls, the authors found that SCH was linked to a higher risk of spontaneous abortion and stillbirth, abruption, preterm delivery, and preterm premature rupture of membranes, but not small for gestational age or pre-eclampsia [10].

Aspirin, or acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), is a widely used vasoactive drug that irreversibly inhibits the enzyme cyclooxygenase in platelets, limiting thromboxane production [21]. ASA has been demonstrated to improve intra-ovarian ascularity, uterine perfusion, and endometrial receptivity [22]. In some regimens, ASA is often used during ovulation induction. Heparin and ASA have both been used to treat recurrent pregnancy loss (RPL), affecting both the immune and coagulation systems [22]. The effects of ASA on platelet aggregation inhibition are considered to interact with heparin to promote and enhance implantation.

ASA is also frequently administered during pregnancy as an efficient treatment for pre-eclampsia that is safe for both mother and fetus [23]. In addition to treating pre-eclampsia, studies have demonstrated that using ASA reduces the risk of premature birth [24, 25]. Weckstein et al. reported that low-dose ASA increased endometrial receptiveness in oocyte receptors [26].

SCH are most likely produced by low pressure bleeding from tears in the placenta's marginal veins [27]. Although SCH has been linked to aberrant pregnancy outcomes, the association remains unclear, with SCH being present in 20% to 70% of these abnormal outcomes [27,28]. In the 2003 study by Nagy et al., the total incidence of hematomas was 3.1% in a general obstetrics population, accounting for 230 of 7405 singleton births [1]. In a large retrospective analysis, Norman et al. found that 1,081 out of 63,966 (1.7%) women before 22 weeks gestation had SCH [6]. Their frequency of SCH is lower than that reported here, most likely because their recording period, 1994-2008, began when sonographic technology was less sensitive to detecting SCH.

As a matter of fact, data from a previous study that suggested a cut-off value of 32 ml for the size of hematoma, with a higher rate of miscarriage for hematomas larger than 32 ml with 81% sensitivity in ROC analysis [18].

Similar to this, in a prior study on the prognosis of first-trimester hematomas that are very large (> 50% of the gestational sac), the authors noted the association between very large hematomas and adverse outcomes in nearly half of the pregnancies, along with worse outcomes when the hematoma was diagnosed at a young gestational age [29].

According to data from a study, women who had multiple pregnancies or other risk factors for poor placentation had a greater prevalence of SCH, which may imply a link between SCH and poor placentation [30]. In a different study [6], it was discovered that SCH was related to advanced maternal age or greater parity. However, there was no evidence of a significant relationship between maternal age or parity and the occurrence or size of a hematoma during pregnancy in the literature [18].

ASA is currently widely administered to women with preeclampsia [24], but our findings suggest that using ASA may increase the likelihood of developing a SCH during the first trimester. Based on these findings, we recommend that ASA not be initiated in women with a history of pre-eclampsia until the second trimester. The U.S. Preventative Services Task Force recommends

low-dose ASA (81 mg) for women with a history of preeclampsia, multiple gestations, chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, renal disease, or autoimmune disease [31]. A recent cost-benefit analysis of low-dose ASA prophylaxis for pre-eclampsia prevention found that providing universal prophylaxis to all pregnant women in the United States would reduce morbidity [32]. However, this theoretical model failed to account for the higher morbidity associated with the predicted four-fold increase in SCH. As a result, this supports the U.S. Preventative Services Task Force's advice to postpone the introduction of prophylactic low-dose ASA until the second trimester.

During the first 20 weeks of pregnancy, the presence of SCH was also said to increase the risk of miscarriage in patients who experienced vaginal bleeding and threatened abortion, but it had no discernible effect on other outcome measures, such as the gestational week at delivery, the birth weight, and the method of delivery [8].

Additionally, the investigators validated the link between SCH and a higher probability of spontaneous abortion in a meta-analysis of six trials, although they found no evidence of a significant difference between SCH and the threatened abortion group in terms of premature birth rates or method of delivery [14].

Furthermore, it has been proven that endometrial and subendometrial vascularity is much higher in pregnant patients with live births than in those with miscarriage, which strengthens the case for using ASA [33]. According to studies, given the lack of demonstrated efficacy and the actual risk of harm, ASA should not be regularly suggested to women having assisted conception [22, 34-36]. Maternal age has been reported to have a crucial role in the factors that increase the incidence of SCH, along with other independent variables such as gestational age and hematoma size [36].

Additionally, this seems noteworthy in light of the hypothesis that SCH increases the likelihood of fetal distress during pregnancy. This hypothesis is supported by the association between SCH and an increased risk of operative vaginal delivery (vacuum extraction) or cesarean delivery, as well as a higher risk of placental abruption or abnormal placentation when compared to pregnancies without SCH [1]. As a result, the presence of SCH was also observed to be linked to unfavorable neonatal outcomes, such as an increased risk of short gestational age at delivery, low birth weight, a poor Apgar score at 1 and 5 minutes, and a greater chance of admission to the NICU as compared to control pregnant women [7].

Previous investigations likewise found no link between the size of the SCH and preterm labor, spontaneous abortion, or gestational diabetes [37]. They also found no relationship between the size of the SCH and an increased risk of pregnancy-induced hypertension, pre-eclampsia, or gestational diabetes [1, 6, 30]. Additionally, it was noted that neither the position nor the location of the placental hematoma had any bearing on the pregnancy's prognosis [29], although a posteriorly positioned SCH had a stronger correlation with fetal distress [1].

Additionally, despite the fact that use of low dose aspirin [38], heparin [39], or thrombolytic therapy [40] has been suggested to be associated with an increased risk of developing a SCH during the first trimester of pregnancy. It has also been documented in other research [38, 41, 42] that heparin or progesterone medication had no discernible effect on the risk of or improvement in early pregnancy loss, respectively. Following this study, which found an increased frequency of SCH linked with the use of ASA 81 mg, numerous investigations found no benefit from the use of ASA 81 mg [32,33]. We continue to utilize ASA 81 mg pre-conceptionally for up to 36 weeks, as well as in women with antiphospholipid syndrome and RPL [43].

Although the precise pathophysiology of the adverse pregnancy outcomes associated with SCH has not yet been elucidated, premature perfusion of the intervillous space, mechanical effects of the hematoma, and impaired angiogenesis causing the hematoma have all been proposed as potential predisposing factors [8,10,30,44,45].

Some publications underline the potential value of taking into account parameters related to fetal distress (Apgar scores) or gestational week at miscarriage in order to better understand the pregnancy outcomes in women with SCH [1,8]. If women develop SCH while taking ASA 81 mg and heparin, we cease the ASA. Regardless of the initial diagnosis of infertility, RPL, or control status, participants in this study had a higher frequency of SCH when using ASA. This apparent link between ASA and SCH warrants additional exploration in future studies. Previous research has found a link between SCH and bad outcomes, thus proper counseling, therapy, and patient care may be recommended. Patients should be informed on the risks and advantages of ASA use during pregnancy.

In conclusion, the results of the study show that women who are diagnosed with SCH in the first trimester have an increased risk of having an unfavorable pregnancy outcome, including lower gestational ages at delivery and higher rates of first trimester bleeding regardless of the size of the hematoma, but also an increased risk of preterm delivery, delivery before 37 weeks' gestation, first trimester vaginal bleeding, early pregnancy loss, placental abruption, and intrauterine growth restriction, this is especially true for women who have larger-sized hematomas.

These results highlight the need of serial sonographic examination follow-up of pregnant women with SCH in order to monitor the clinical course of SCH and to detect predicted unfavorable pregnancy outcomes such IUGR early. It may be helpful in clinical settings for future research to compare different approaches to assessing the impact of the size and location of SCH on pregnancy outcomes, including the perinatal period.

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